

THE USE OF ICT TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Mastering the methodology for guiding the game process is considered a key condition for successfully conducting games. The challenges of integrating ICT technologies into school practice are also addressed.*

Keywords: *national, modern, organizations, assistant, employee responsibilities, social.*

Problems of Integrating ICT Technologies into School Practice.

“Games and Tasks on Informatics” as an Additional Educational Service.

With the increasing demands on the education system in modern society, the intrinsic connection between enhancing educational quality and the informatization of the educational process has long been recognized. Schools, as integral parts of society, reflect the same issues found throughout the nation. Therefore, it is crucial to organize the learning process in such a way that students remain active, engaged, and interested in their education.

The combination of traditional teaching methods and modern approaches can assist teachers in addressing this challenging task, especially through the use of information technologies, including computers. Informatization is now regarded as one of the main methods for modernizing the education system. This transformation is not only tied to advancements in engineering and technology but is primarily linked to the development of the information society, where the core value is the ability to handle information and contribute to personal development through various projects and programs.

The primary goal of teaching community is to identify and nurture each child's abilities, creating conditions for the development of a well-rounded individual who possesses strong foundational knowledge and can adapt to contemporary life. Informatization of education should be viewed as a critical tool for achieving this goal. It involves a series of sequential tasks that outline the stages of modernizing the education system, such as providing technical equipment, developing didactic tools, and creating new teaching technologies.

The informatization of society has significantly transformed everyday life. As educators, we must keep pace with the times and guide children into the world of new technologies. It's essential that we not only adapt to these changes but also actively facilitate students' understanding and engagement with the technological advancements that shape their learning experiences.

What is ICT?

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) refer to the methods and tools used to work with information resources. According to I.G. Zakharova, "Information technologies are a set of knowledge about the methods of collecting, processing, and transmitting information to obtain new data about the studied object".

ICT encompasses specialized methods, software, and technical tools (such as audio-visual devices and computers) that are applied in pedagogical technology for working with information. They are person-centered educational technologies, contributing to the implementation of differentiated and individual approaches in education.

The significance of utilizing ICT in the development of school-aged children is paramount today. Information technologies greatly expand the opportunities for parents, teachers, and specialists in early education. Modern computers facilitate the comprehensive and successful development of children's abilities.

Unlike traditional technical teaching tools, ICT allows for the enhancement of not just a child's knowledge through carefully structured information but also the intellectual and creative skills that are crucial during early childhood. This includes the ability to independently acquire new knowledge.

The ability of computers to process text, graphics, sound, speech, and video data simultaneously enables specialists to create new activity tools that significantly differ from existing toys. This evolution imposes new quality demands on preschool education, where the primary task is to enrich the child's personality and developmental potential.

Thus, the integration of information technologies into the preschool education and upbringing system is essential. Practical experience shows that this integration markedly increases children's interest in lessons and enhances their cognitive abilities.

The use of new, unconventional methods of explanation and reinforcement, especially in the form of games, enhances children's voluntary attention and helps develop it further. ICT ensures a person-centered approach, increasing the amount of material available for review. Furthermore, the repetition of program material is crucial for preschoolers, and the diversity of presentation forms holds significant importance.

Computer games outside the classroom can significantly aid in reinforcing children's knowledge. They can be used for individual lessons with children who are either ahead or lagging behind their peers in cognitive development. These games are essential for developing mental skills necessary for intellectual activities, such as perception, attention, memory, thinking, and fine motor skills.

Computer programs promote independence and foster self-regulation skills. Young children often require more assistance in completing tasks and need their actions to be confirmed step by step, while automated correctness checks allow teachers to work simultaneously with other children.

Through computer games, children can engage with learning in a dynamic way. Games represent a form of practical thinking, where children interact with knowledge, experiences, impressions, and actions that manifest socially within the game context. They learn to assign meaning to neutral objects in the game, which becomes significant within the gaming narrative. This ability is a key psychological foundation for integrating computers as a tool in the play of preschool-aged children.

The game activities of preschoolers enriched with computer tools lead to the emergence of cognitive neoplasms (theoretical thinking, advanced imagination, the ability to predict outcomes, design-oriented thinking, and etc.), which contribute to a significant increase in their creative abilities.

When compared to traditional forms of teaching school-aged children, computers offer several advantages:

Engaging Presentation: Information is presented in a playful manner on the computer screen, which greatly enhances interest.

Accessible Information: The type of information provided is easily understandable for preschoolers, using visuals that resonate with their developmental stage.

Attention-Grabbing Features: Actions, sounds, and animations captivate children's attention for extended periods.

Stimulating Problem-Solving: Challenging tasks encourage children to engage in cognitive activities and find correct solutions independently.

Personalized Learning: Computers allow for the individualization of learning experiences tailored to each child's pace and needs.

Self-Regulated Learning: Children can control the speed and amount of learning tasks they need to complete during gameplay.

Boosting Confidence: Preschool teachers gain confidence in their ability to guide children, as they observe students achieving various tasks.

Simulating Real-Life Situations: Computers enable the simulation of real-life scenarios that might not be feasible to experience directly (such as rocket launches or natural disasters).

Patient Learning Environment: Computers are "patient" tools that never scold children for mistakes but rather encourage them to correct their errors independently.

These advantages illustrate how computer-based learning can create an engaging and effective educational environment for young learners.

Where Can ICT Technologies Be Used in Schools?

The effectiveness of computerization in early childhood education institutions depends on the quality of software tools and the ability to use them wisely and skillfully in the educational process. Information and communication technologies can be applied in various aspects of a preschool setting:

Educational Process: ICT can enhance both teaching and learning activities, providing interactive and engaging resources for children.

Methodological Work: Teachers can utilize ICT in their methodological tasks, improving lesson planning, resource development, and assessment methods.

Collaboration with Parents and the Community: ICT can facilitate communication and collaboration between the educational institution, parents, and the wider community, promoting shared involvement in the educational process.

Use of ICT in the Educational Process

The use of computers in learning and development for preschoolers can be broadly categorized into direct and indirect methods:

Direct Use: Involves children engaging with educational software, games, and applications designed to enhance learning and cognitive skills.

Indirect Use: Encompasses the integration of ICT in teaching practices, such as using presentations, multimedia resources, and digital storytelling to enrich the learning experience.

1. Teaching and Development Through Mediation

It is challenging to envision modern education without Internet resources. The Internet offers vast opportunities for educational services. Email, search engines, and electronic conferences have become integral components of contemporary education. Online, you can find information about early education and development, innovative schools and kindergartens, as well as foreign institutions, and even establish contact with leading specialists in the field of early development education.

Consequently, in recent years, the Internet has been widely implemented not only in schools but also in preschool education. The volume of digital information resources for nurturing and developing children is continually increasing.

The Internet is increasingly available for use in the educational process. The opportunities provided by online resources allow specialists working in the preschool education system to address a range of pressing tasks.

Access to Additional Information: This includes data that may not be available in printed publications for various reasons.

Diverse Visual Materials: This encompasses a variety of visual resources, both static and dynamic (such as animations and video content).

Democratic Dissemination of Ideas: In an information society, online resources represent the most democratic method for distributing new methodological ideas and didactic materials, accessible to educators regardless of their location or income level.

Using Internet resources makes the learning process for preschool-aged children informative, engaging, and convenient. Educators can utilize electronic resources as part of their informational and methodological support when preparing for lessons, exploring new methods, and selecting visual aids.

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